

THE PERFORMANCE OF THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOSET COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO LOW-VELOCITY AND HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The impact performance of cross-ply thermoplastic and thermoset composites, under low-velocity and high-velocity impact loading, is assessed by conducting drop-weight and gas gun experiments. Typical load versus time and load versus displacement traces, for both types of composites, are obtained from the drop-weight experiments undertaken at various impact energy levels. The out-of-plane displacement of the composite specimens, subjected to high-velocity impacts, is measured using three-dimensional Digital Image Correlation (3D-DIC). A portable C-scan system is employed to provide an assessment of the damaged area of the test specimens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fibre reinforced-polymers (CFRPs) have been extensively employed on modern commercial aircraft, where the strength-to-weight ratio has a direct beneficial influence on performance and operating costs [1–3]. Such composites can be based upon thermoplastic or thermoset polymeric matrices. However, all types of CFRPs are vulnerable to impact loading and this can lead to sub-surface delamination [4–6].

The impact performance of thermoplastic and thermoset composites subjected to low-velocity and high-velocity impact loading have been evaluated and compared. For example, Dorey et al. [7] compared the impact performance of carbon-fibre reinforced PEEK (CF/PEEK) and carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy (CF/epoxy) with similar fibre volume fractions and lay-ups. The greater matrix toughness of the CF/PEEK caused less splitting and delamination in the specimens. Sjöblom et al. [8] have confirmed the superior performance of CF/PEEK composites compared with a CF/epoxy using drop-weight tests. The energy absorption curves and failure mechanisms of both types of materials were determined.

With regard to the structural failure of the composite laminates under high-velocity impact, e.g. bird-strikes, hailstone impacts and runway debris, many researchers have focused on the performance of composite materials subjected to high-velocity impact loading [9–11]. For example, López-Puente et al. [9] studied the energy absorption ability of CFRPs, experimentally and numerically, at test velocities ranging from 60 m.s⁻¹ to 550 m.s⁻¹. The ballistic limit and the relationship between the damage area and impact energy of the specimens were determined. Pernas-Sánchez et al. [10] simulated hailstone impact, using real ice projectiles with two diameters, on CF/epoxy composites over a velocity range of 50 m.s⁻¹

to 250 m.s^{-1} . The performance of these composites was also evaluated by measuring the delamination area via ultrasonic techniques. Wang et al. [11] studied the ballistic resistance and energy absorption efficiency of the CFRPs for velocities ranging from 180 m.s^{-1} to 2000 m.s^{-1} . Superior energy absorption efficiency of the CFRP composites was observed when compared with a stainless steel plate.

In the present study, both a drop-weight test rig and a gas-gun test were employed to perform impact tests on both CF/epoxy and CF/PEEK composites. For the gas-gun experiments, three-dimensional Digital Image Correlation (3D-DIC) was employed to measure the deformation of the rear face of the specimen during the impact event. The performance under these different impact threats was quantified, so as to help understand the influence of drop-tool and foreign body impact on vulnerable aircraft structures using CFRPs. Ultrasonic C-scan equipment, using a portable device, appropriate for in-service inspection, was employed to provide an assessment of the damage caused from the different types of impact loading.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Material system

Two types of CFRP (i.e. CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy) were fabricated for the drop-weight and gas gun testing. They employed either a semi-crystalline poly(ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) matrix or a conventional thermosetting epoxy matrix. The CF/PEEK composite employed carbon-fibre AS4 ($\sigma_{\text{tensile}} = 4413 \text{ MPa}$; $E = 231 \text{ GPa}$) and the CF/epoxy employed T700 carbon-fibre ($\sigma_{\text{tensile}} = 4900 \text{ MPa}$; $E = 230 \text{ GPa}$). Both types of CFRP had the same $[90_3/0_3]_{2s}$ layup and a similar ply thickness which, when consolidated, gave the same overall thickness of 3 mm for the CFRP (CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy) composites. To achieve this, fibre volume fraction of the CF/PEEK and the CF/epoxy were slightly different, but it was approximately 65% for both types of CFRP. The CF/PEEK panels were fabricated at the University of Nottingham using hot-press moulding at up to $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whilst the CF/epoxy panels were manufactured at the AVIC Composite Corporation via autoclave processing at up to 180°C . Impact test specimens were cut from large plaques into $150 \times 100 \text{ mm}$ test specimens.

2.2 Instrumentation

The rigid impactor drop-weight tests were performed using an INSTRON CEAST 9350 drop tower with a hemispherical $\text{Ø}12.7 \text{ mm}$ instrumented steel impactor, which had a mass of 5.37 kg. The test system is shown in Fig. 1. The impact energy was varied by adjusting the height of the impactor. The panels to be tested were positioned on a secured platform and fixed by four toggle clamps, as described in the ASTM 7136 standard [12]. A catching system was employed in the test to avoid a second impact.

Figure 1 : Experimental set-up for the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

A gas-gun, shown in Figs. 2 and 3, was used for the high-velocity rigid impacts. The 3D-DIC speckle mapping technique was employed to monitor the deformation response from the rear face of the specimens. A hemispherical $\varnothing 12.7$ mm aluminium-alloy projectile, which has a nominal weight of 7 g, was assembled with a sabot to achieve a reproducible impact velocity. The velocity was measured using two pairs of sensors located at the end of the barrel. Two synchronized Phantom Miro M/R/LC310 cameras at 29,000 fps, were positioned, at the rear of the target.

A portable ‘Sonatest Prisma’ ultrasonic C-scan (5 MHz) system, shown in Fig. 4, was used to assess the resulting damage.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up for the high-velocity (gas gun) impact tests.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of the experimental set-up for the high-velocity (gas-gun) impact tests.

Figure 4: The portable 'Prisma' C-scan system.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Low-velocity impact (drop-weight) tests

For the drop-weight impacts, typical load versus time traces for the CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy composites, for different energy levels, are shown in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. In these traces, at the initial stage, the increase in load is due to the elastic response of the specimens under the impact loading and following a decrease in the load, which indicates initial damage, there is a further rise to the maximum load. Delamination and matrix cracking, caused by the impact, start to propagate after the initial damage has occurred. The impactor then rebounds, due to the reaction forces from the specimen,

to produce a smooth decrease in the load. It should be noted that higher peak loads were always observed for higher impact energies. However, the load at initial damage was relatively independent of the impact energy level. The CF/PEEK composites showed a higher peak load than the CF/epoxy specimens for all the impact energy levels employed

Figure 5: Load versus time curves for the CF/PEEK specimens impacted at 4.5 J, 7.5 J and 10.5 J for the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

Figure 6: Load versus time curves for the CF/epoxy specimens impacted at 4.5 J, 7.5 J and 10.5 J for the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

The displacement of the impactor was recorded by the CEAST drop tower instrumentation. Typical load versus displacement traces for the CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy composites, for different energy levels, are shown in Figs. 7 and 8, respectively. After damage initiation, damage started to propagate with the increase in the load and corresponding displacement. The peak load was followed by a smooth reduction in both the load and displacement during the rebound phase of the impactor. It was noted that an indentation under the impactor, on the front surface, was observed in all the specimens.

Figure 7: Load versus displacement curves for the CF/PEEK specimens impacted at 4.5 J, 7.5 J and 10.5 J for the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

Figure 8: Load versus displacement curves for the CF/epoxy specimens impacted at 4.5 J, 7.5 J and 10.5 J for the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

C-scan maps of the CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy specimens are shown for the different energy levels, in Fig. 9. C-scan maps show the delamination as a function of depth through the thickness of the tested specimens. The red colour represents the front (impacted) surface and the blue colour represents the rear surface. As shown, less damage is observed (a) in the specimens impacted using a lower energy and (b) for the CF/PEEK specimens in comparison with the CF/epoxy specimens. Thus, it can be concluded that the CF/PEEK composites have better damage tolerance than the CF/epoxy.

Figure 9: C-scan maps for the CF/PEEK (top row) and CF/epoxy (bottom row) specimens impacted at 4.5 J, 7.5 J and 10.5 J using the low-velocity (drop-weight) impact tests.

3.2 High-velocity impact (gas-gun) tests

For the high-velocity gas-gun experiments, the deformation of the composite specimens are obtained from the 3D-DIC results. An example of the 3D-DIC result of the CF/epoxy specimen impacted at a velocity of $46 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 10, as an out-of-plane displacement map and out-of-plane displacement profile during the loading and unloading phases. A maximum out-of-plane displacement of 2.13 mm was measured, and the behaviour of the specimens in both phases can be found via the deformation profile across the middle section of the panel. A feature of the high velocity tests is the onset of damage on the rear face, as evident by the localised increased displacement.

Figure 10: An experimental result for the CF/epoxy panel impacted using a rigid (aluminium-alloy) projectile with a velocity of 46 m.s^{-1} showing the out-of-plane displacement maps and out-of-plane displacement profile during the loading and unloading phases.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study the impact performance of the CF/PEEK and CF/epoxy composites subjected to low-velocity impact has been evaluated. The peak loads and the loads for the onset of initial damage, were both greater for the CF/PEEK composites compared to the CF/epoxy composites, for the same impact energy levels. Further, a lower extent of damaged area, as determined via the C-scan system, was observed in the CF/PEEK laminates, which again confirmed their superior damage resistance. The impact response of both types of specimens subjected to the high-velocity impact loading will be presented in detail at ICCM22.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G.M. Newaz (Ed.). *Advances in Thermoplastic Matrix Composite Materials*. ASTM International, USA; 1989.
- [2] A.C. Long. *Composites forming technologies*. Elsevier, UK; 2014.
- [3] H. Liu, B.G. Falzon, W. Tan. Predicting the Compression-After-Impact (CAI) strength of damage-tolerant hybrid unidirectional/woven carbon-fibre reinforced composite laminates. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf*. 2018;105:189–202.
- [4] J. Liu, C. Kaboglu, H. Liu, B.R.K. Blackman. High speed digital image correlation for impact performance of thermoplastic and thermoset composites. *18th Eur Conf Compos Mater*. 2018.

- [5] H. Liu, B.G. Falzon, W. Tan. Experimental and numerical studies on the impact response of damage-tolerant hybrid unidirectional/woven carbon-fibre reinforced composite laminates. *Compos Part B Eng.* 2018;136:101–18.
- [6] H. Liu, B.G. Falzon, S. Li, W. Tan, J. Liu, H. Chai, et al. Compressive failure of woven fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites with an open-hole: An experimental and numerical study. *Compos Struct.* 2019;213:108–17.
- [7] G. Dorey, S.M. Bishop, P.T. Curtis. On the impact performance of carbon fibre laminates with epoxy and PEEK matrices. *Compos Sci Technol.* 1985;23:221–37.
- [8] P.O. Sjoblom, J.T. Hartness, T.M. Cordell. On low-velocity impact testing of composite materials. *J Compos Mater.* 1988;22:30–52.
- [9] J. López-Puente, R. Zaera, C. Navarro Ugena. High energy impact on woven laminates. *J Phys IV.* 2003;110:639-44.
- [10] J. Pernas-Sánchez, J.A. Artero-Guerrero, D. Varas, J. López-Puente. Experimental analysis of ice sphere impacts on unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates. *Int J Impact Eng.* 2016;96:1–10.
- [11] B. Wang, J. Xiong, X. Wang, L. Ma, G.Q. Zhang, L.Z. Wu, et al. Energy absorption efficiency of carbon fiber reinforced polymer laminates under high velocity impact. *Mater Des.* 2013;50:140–8.
- [12] D7136/D7136M-05 Standard Test Method for Measuring the Damage Resistance of a Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite to a Drop-Weight Impact Event. ASTM International, USA; 2005.